

A Study on Antibiotic Sensitivity of Bacterial Isolates and Their Correlation with Hematological Parameters in Urinary Tract Infections

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Abstract

Background:

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) remain a significant health concern among women, particularly during pregnancy and in individuals with diabetes. Emerging resistance to commonly prescribed antibiotics and variations in hematological parameters necessitate comprehensive evaluation for effective clinical management.

Objectives:

To determine the antibiotic sensitivity profile of bacterial isolates in UTI cases and evaluate the correlation of these infections with hematological parameters in symptomatic female patients.

Methods:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on 112 urine samples from symptomatic women at a tertiary hospital in Rajasthan. Bacterial cultures were performed, and isolates were identified using conventional methods and confirmed by the VITEK 2 Compact system. Antibiotic susceptibility was assessed following CLSI guidelines. Hematological parameters including Hb, TLC, DLC, ESR, RBC, and platelet indices were analyzed using Mindray BC-6200. Statistical analyses were conducted using descriptive statistics and independent t-tests, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Results:

Out of 112 samples, 63 (56.25%) showed bacterial growth. *Escherichia coli* was the predominant isolate (73.01%). High resistance was observed to Ampicillin (96.67%), Ciprofloxacin (96.43%), and Cefixime (96.43%), while Fosfomycin (89.29%) and Nitrofurantoin (78.43%) showed good sensitivity. Hematologically, 60.71% of patients were anemic (Hb < 12 g/dL), and 44.64% had elevated ESR levels. Statistically significant differences were observed in ESR ($p = 0.00290$), RBC count ($p = 0.03439$), PCV ($p = 0.00857$), and platelet count ($p = 0.02235$) between culture-positive and culture-negative groups.

Conclusion:

The study highlights the alarming antibiotic resistance among UTI pathogens and emphasizes the diagnostic value of hematological parameters. Regular surveillance of antibiotic susceptibility and inclusion of hematological profiling can enhance UTI diagnosis and guide appropriate therapy, especially in high-risk populations such as pregnant and diabetic women.

Keywords:

Urinary tract infection, antibiotic resistance, *E. coli*, hematological parameters, VITEK 2, anemia, inflammation

Introduction:

Complicated urinary tract infections happen when something affects the urinary system or weakens the body's ability to fight off infections. Things like blocked urine flow, problems with the nerves that control the bladder, a weak immune system, kidney disease, being pregnant, catheters, or drainage tubes in the body can all make these infections more serious [1]. UTIs are an important contributor to rising illness rates & healthcare costs. In the general population, women are particularly at risk, with 40-50% having experienced at least one UTI episode. [2]. During pregnancy, the amount of blood plasma increases, which makes urine less concentrated. Because of this, up to 70% of pregnant women have sugar in their urine, and this can help bacteria grow. [3]. Infections, especially during pregnancy and in older adults, may occur

without displaying any noticeable symptoms [4]. During pregnancy, asymptomatic bacteriuria is linked to a higher risk of low birth weight and stunted fetal growth [5]. Therefore, it is crucial to detect and treat UTIs to prevent potential complications. Sheikh et al. found that a previous history of urological issues was linked to a higher occurrence of UTIs during pregnancy [6]. The pathogens responsible for UTIs in pregnant women are like those in non-pregnant individuals, with *Escherichia coli* causing 80% to 90% of the infections [7]. The remaining infections are attributed to *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Pseudomonas* species, and *Streptococcus* species [8]. Approximately 5% of all hospitalizations for pregnant patients are related to UTIs, which affect 5–10% of pregnant women [9]. One of the main causes of maternal and perinatal morbidity during pregnancy is urinary tract infections. Pregnancy-related UTIs have been linked to complications such as abortion, low birth weight, anemia, hypertension, premature labor, phlebitis, thrombosis, and persistent pyelonephritis [10]. Pregnancy elevates the risk of UTI. Around the sixth week, physiological changes cause the ureters to start dilating, a condition known as "hydronephrosis of pregnancy," which peaks between 22 and 26 weeks and persists until delivery. Rising levels of progesterone and estrogen during pregnancy reduce the tone of the ureters and bladder [11]. Recent studies in Nigeria have highlighted a growing prevalence of *Klebsiella* species, *Staph. aureus*, *Proteus* species, and *Pseudomonas* species in UTIs during pregnancy [12]. India has earned the title of the diabetic capital of the world, with (UTIs) being the infection that happen most often in people with diabetes. These UTIs can lead to significant kidney damage and even renal failure. Better management of diabetes mellitus (DM) is crucial in safeguarding the urinary tract organs from such harm [13]. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a known contributor to severe and complicated urinary tract infections (UTIs), largely due to its impact on the genitourinary system. [14]. This study gives useful information about how UTIs usually occur, the organisms responsible, and their severity, with a specific focus on the European Association of Urology (EAU) 2015 guidelines for UTIs [15]. Research has indicated that diabetes alone does not appear to significantly affect the rate at which various uropathogens are isolated or their susceptibility to antimicrobial treatments [16]. Pregnancy begins at conception, when a sperm fertilizes an egg to create a zygote, and concludes with childbirth, abortion, or miscarriage [17]. Pregnancy begins at conception, when a sperm fertilizes an egg to create a zygote, and concludes with childbirth, abortion, or miscarriage [18]. As various interventions have emerged to enhance maternal and child health, pregnant women have increasingly become the central focus of numerous health initiatives [19]. Despite the significance of this population, there is limited data available. While pregnancy brings about changes in hematological values, only a few laboratories offer specific reference ranges tailored to pregnant women [20]. As a result, there is a heightened risk of missing critical physiological changes due to underlying pathological conditions and mistakenly interpreting normal alterations as signs of illness [21]. Understanding pregnancy-induced hematological changes is essential for accurate clinical assessment and proper care of pregnant women [22]. CBC is a diagnostic test that gives information on the different types of cells present in a patient's blood [23]. The CBC includes platelets, WBC, and RBC [24]. An average adult has approximately 5 liters of blood, consisting

of 2 liters of blood cells and 3 liters of plasma. In the bone marrow, hematopoietic stem cells produce all blood cells [25]. During pregnancy, the typical reference range for hemoglobin (Hgb) is 11-12 g/dL. Critical Hgb levels are considered to be <5 g/dL, which can lead to heart failure, and >20 g/dL, which may result in hemoconcentration and an increased risk of clotting [26]. Starting around the 16th week of gestation, hemoglobin (Hgb) levels begin to decrease due to the expansion of plasma volume. A similar pattern is observed in red blood cell (RBC) count and hematocrit (Hct) levels [27]. Because broad-spectrum antibiotics are widely used in both human and animal feed, the prevalence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria has increased. Among these are *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella* species, *Streptococcus* species, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus faecalis*, and *Escherichia coli*. These UTI-causing microbes have been shown to exhibit drug resistance. Most often encountered in hospital settings, antibiotic resistance is also becoming more prevalent in community-acquired UTIs. In these infections, gram-positive cocci like *Staphylococci* and gram-negative organisms like *Klebsiella* are becoming more common [28].

Methodology:

This descriptive study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology, where 112 midstream clean-catch urine samples were collected from symptomatic female patients. Samples were cultured and organisms were identified using conventional methods and confirmed by VITEK 2 Compact system. Antibiotic sensitivity testing was carried out using the same system as per CLSI guidelines [29].

The Mindray BC-6200 automated hematology analyzer was used to measure hematological parameters such as hemoglobin (Hb), total leukocyte count (TLC), differential leukocyte count (DLC), ESR, and platelet count. Descriptive statistics and the independent t-test were used to assess the data. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value < 0.05 [30].

RESULTS

This was a descriptive study with comparative evaluation of hematological parameters between culture-positive and culture-negative symptomatic female patients.

The present study was conducted on a total number of 112 urine samples collected from women (both pregnant and non-pregnant) presenting with symptoms suggestive of urinary tract infection (UTI) during the period of January 2025 to March 2025 (3 months). Out of 112 urine samples, 49 (43.75%) were sterile and 63 (56.25%) were bacterial growth.

Out of 112 patients, 39 (34.82%) were pregnant, while 73 (65.18%) were not. This highlights the importance of studying UTIs in both pregnant and non-pregnant populations, as hormonal and anatomical changes during pregnancy can influence UTI prevalence.

Among the 112 urine samples analyzed, 63 (56.25%) tested positive for urinary tract infections (UTI), while 49 (43.75%) showed no microbial growth.

While the Fig 1 provided the patient distribution based on age groups, the highest cases was seen in patients aged 31–40 years 45 (40.18%), showing that middle-aged persons were more susceptible to UTIs. This might have due to various reasons: increased sexual activity, pregnancy, or age-related physiological changes. Least affected were patients above 70 years 3 (2.68%).

Fig No: 1 Frequency distribution of age of patients

Table 1 showed the distribution of antibiotic resistance and sensitivity among the bacterial isolates obtained from symptomatic female patients with urinary tract infection. The table highlighted that Ampicillin had the highest resistance rate, with 58 isolates (96.67%) showing resistance and only 2 (3.33%) being sensitive. Ciprofloxacin and Cefixime also showed high levels of resistance, with 54 (96.43%) and 27 (96.43%) resistant isolates respectively. Norfloxacin (94.55%), Ceftriaxone (93.22%), and Nalidixic Acid (96.00%) similarly demonstrated very high resistance rates.

On the other hand, the antibiotics that showed good sensitivity included Fosfomycin, which was effective in 50 isolates (89.29%), followed by Nitrofurantoin (78.43%) and Colistin (80.00%). Ertapenem also showed promising sensitivity in 75.00% of the isolates. Moderate sensitivity was noted for Amikacin (65.12%) and Gentamicin (64.81%). Tazobactam was effective in 66.67% of isolates, showing a balanced pattern of sensitivity and resistance.

Table 1: Distribution of resistance and sensitivity pattern of antibiotics

Antibiotics	Resistance		Sensitive	
	Frequency	In %	Frequency	In %
Ampicillin	58	96.67%	2	3.33%
Amoxicillin/Clavulanic Acid	21	75.00%	7	25.00%
Ticarcillin	30	96.77%	1	3.23%

Tazobactam	21	33.33%	42	66.67%
Cefalotin	23	88.46%	3	11.54%
Cefoxitin	13	52.00%	12	48.00%
Ceftazidime	35	81.40%	8	18.60%
Ceftriaxone	55	93.22%	4	6.78%
Ertapenem	4	25.00%	12	75.00%
Amikacin	15	34.88%	28	65.12%
Gentamicin	19	35.19%	35	64.81%
Fosfomycin	6	10.71%	50	89.29%
Nalidixic Acid	24	96.00%	1	4.00%
Ciprofloxacin	54	96.43%	2	3.57%
Norfloxacin	52	94.55%	3	5.45%
Ofloxacin	20	90.91%	2	9.09%
Nitrofurantoin	11	21.57%	40	78.43%
Trimethoprim/ Sulfamethoxazole	18	64.29%	10	35.71%
Cefixime	27	96.43%	1	3.57%
Colistine	4	20.00%	16	80.00%

ESR (Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate) is an inflammatory marker. About 44.64% of patients had elevated ESR (>20 mm), indicating an active infection or systemic inflammation, which correlates with UTI presence

Hemoglobin levels were low (<12 g/dL) in 60.71% of patients, suggesting a high incidence of anemia. This could be due to chronic infection, nutritional deficiency, or other underlying conditions.

Figure:2 Frequency distribution of hemoglobin of samples

Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) was normal in most patients (72.32%), but elevated in 27.68%, indicating an immune response to infection. Eosinophil levels were within normal range (1.0–6.0%) in 46.43% of patients. A small number (3.57%) showed eosinophilia, which can occur in

parasitic infections or allergic reactions. Basophil levels were normal (0.0–1.0%) in all patients. This indicates no allergic or chronic inflammatory response affecting basophil levels. 65.18% of patients had RBC counts below normal, reinforcing the observation of anemia in most cases.

Packed Cell Volume (PCV) was below 32% in 30.36% of cases, another indicator of anemia or low red cell mass. Most patients had normal MCV values (78–98 FL), suggesting normocytic anemia. Some had values <78, indicating microcytic anemia, possibly due to iron deficiency. Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH) was below 26 pg. in 30.36% of samples, suggesting hypochromia which is typical of iron deficiency anemia. Most patients (90.18%) had normal MCHC values. This suggests normochromic, although a small portion had lower or higher values. RDW-CV measures variation in red blood cell size. 38.39% had values >15%, indicating anisocytosis which may be associated with iron deficiency or mixed anemia types. Most patients had normal platelet counts (82.14%). However, 15.18% showed thrombocytopenia, which could occur due to infections or other hematological abnormalities. MPV was elevated (>12 fL) in 53.57% of patients, suggesting increased platelet production or activation, often seen in infections.

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistical values (minimum, maximum, median, mean, and standard deviation) for age and hematological parameters of the patients. The mean age was 38.5 years, and the average hemoglobin was 11.3 g/dL, indicating mild anemia on average. The wide range of ESR (3 to 120 mm/hr.) and elevated mean value of 33.1 mm/hr. supports the presence of inflammation. Mean TLC was $10 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ with a large standard deviation, reflecting the variability in immune responses. Platelet and RBC parameters mostly fall within expected ranges, but with noticeable deviations in values like MPV and RDW-CV, hinting at underlying inflammation or hematologic variation.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of age & hematological parameters of samples

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Median (IQR)	Mean \pm SD
Age (In Yrs.)	18	92	33 (30-47.25)	38.5 \pm 14.6
ESR 1 ST HR MM	3	120	18 (13.75-50.75)	33.1 \pm 29.95
Hemoglobin (In gm/dL)	5.5	15.9	11.7 (10.3-12.7)	11.3 \pm 2.04
TLC THS/UL	0.27	38.72	8.19 (5.35-11.72)	10 \pm 6.96
Neutrophils (In %)	17.9	96.6	78.4 (68.1-84.4)	75.3 \pm 13.1
Lymphocytes (In %)	1.7	78.2	19.2 (12.5-28.05)	20.8 \pm 11.75
Monocytes (In %)	0	8	3 (1.5-3.5)	2.71 \pm 1.67
Eosinophils (In %)	0	9	1.1 (0.2-2.6)	1.59 \pm 1.74
Basophils (In %)	0	1	0.1 (0.0-0.3)	0.21 \pm 0.24
TRBC millions/cu.mm	1.92	5.9	4.38 (3.74-4.6)	4.14 \pm 0.78
PCV (In %)	16.8	46.2	36.35 (31.48-39.43)	35.05 \pm 6.48

MCV (In FL)	59	100.4	85.7 (80.28-89.2)	83.65 ± 8.07
MCH (PG)	18.3	32.9	27.55 (25.6-29.03)	27.11 ± 3.17
MCHC (In gm/dL)	29.8	36	32.2 (31.4-33.3)	32.33 ± 1.32
RDW-CV (In %)	11.6	28.1	14.15 (13.5-15.7)	14.85 ± 2.08
Platelet Count ×10³/UL	2	644	190 (152-284)	218 ± 103.94
PDW (In %)	13.5	17.5	16.3 (16.1-16.8)	16.39 ±0.62
MPV FL	7.5	16.9	12.5 (11.28-14.1)	12.54 ± 2.13

This table focuses on the antibiotic susceptibility of a limited number (n=3) of Gram-positive isolates. Most of these isolates showed high resistance (66.7%) to antibiotics such as Benzylpenicillin, Ciprofloxacin, and Gentamicin. Moderate sensitivity was observed to Linezolid, Teicoplanin, Vancomycin, and Tigecycline. These results emphasize the growing resistance even among Gram-positive uropathogens and the need for culture-based antibiotic selection.

Figure No: 3 Resistance and sensitivity pattern of antibiotics

Table 3 compares hematological parameters according to the type of bacterial isolate (No Growth, E. coli, and Others). Patients with no growth had the highest mean ESR (42.16 mm/hr), whereas those infected with E. coli had higher hemoglobin levels (11.73 g/dL) and RBC counts (4.36 million/cu.mm). TLC was higher in the NG group, possibly due to undetected infections or other systemic inflammation. These differences highlight the physiological impact of bacterial infections and provide insight into host response variations based on the pathogen involved.

Table 3: Bacterial isolates wise level of hematological parameters of patients

Variables	NG	E. Coli	Others
ESR 1 ST HR MM	42.16 ± 32.33	26.07 ± 28.76	25.88 ± 17.65
Hemoglobin (In gm/dL)	11.09 ± 1.88	11.73 ± 2.11	10.96 ± 2.22
TLC THS/UL	11.05 ± 8.54	9.77 ± 6.05	7.90 ± 2.46
Neutrophils (In %)	76.14 ± 12.83	75.18 ± 14.2	73.01 ± 11.06
Lymphocytes (In %)	20.48 ± 10.94	20.66 ± 13.32	22.12 ± 9.89
Monocytes (In %)	2.82 ± 1.65	2.66 ± 1.91	2.54 ± 0.97
Eosinophils (In %)	1.89 ± 1.93	1.2 ± 1.32	1.76 ± 2.07
Basophils (In %)	0.23 ± 0.27	0.2 ± 0.24	0.21 ± 0.14
TRBC millions/cu.mm	3.97 ± 0.63	4.36 ± 0.87	4.02 ± 0.8
PCV (In %)	33.72 ± 5.73	36.53 ± 6.71	34.89 ± 7.39
MCV (In FL)	83.52 ± 7.90	82.77 ± 9.26	86.44 ± 3.63
MCH (PG)	27.18 ± 3.18	26.76 ± 3.58	27.85 ± 1.51
MCHC (In gm/dL)	32.44 ± 1.44	32.24 ± 1.28	32.25 ± 1.09
RDW-CV (In %)	15.09 ± 1.97	14.78 ± 2.47	14.37 ± 0.90
Platelet Count ×10 ³ /UL	238.4 ± 119.8	207.7 ± 93.58	186.88 ± 68.43
PDW (In %)	16.34 ± 0.60	16.43 ± 0.61	16.44 ± 0.69
MPV FL	12.21 ± 1.96	12.5 ± 2.03	13.58 ± 2.62

A comparison of hematological parameters between patients with positive urine culture growth and those without growth was performed using an independent t-test. The mean ESR was significantly lower in the growth group (24.5 ± 23.34 mm/hr) compared to the non-growth group (40.63 ± 30.81 mm/hr) with a statistically significant p-value ($p = 0.00290$).

Hemoglobin levels were slightly higher in the growth group (11.55 ± 2.18 g/dL) than in the non-growth group (11.1 ± 1.88 g/dL), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.23267$).

TLC did not show any significant differences between the two groups (all $p > 0.05$).

A significant difference was observed in Total RBC count, with the growth group having a higher mean value (4.24 ± 0.73 million/cu.mm) than the non-growth group (3.96 ± 0.93 million/cu.mm), and this was statistically significant ($p = 0.03439$).

Packed Cell Volume (PCV) was also significantly higher in the growth group ($36.78 \pm 6.37\%$) compared to the non-growth group ($33.65 \pm 5.97\%$) with $p = 0.00857$.

Other red cell indices such as MCV, MCH, MCHC, and RDW-CV showed no significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

When platelet parameters were compared, the platelet count was significantly lower in the growth group ($202.1 \pm 87.5 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) than in the non-growth group ($248.4 \pm 116.7 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) ($p = 0.02235$). However, PDW and MPV did not differ significantly.

Table 4: Comparing mean of haematological parameters between growth and non-growth samples

Variables	Growth	Non-Growth	t-test	P-Value	Significance
ESR 1 ST HR MM	24.5 ± 23.34	40.63 ± 30.81	-3.047	0.00290	Significant
Haemoglobin (In gm/dL)	11.55 ± 2.18	11.1 ± 1.88	1.200	0.23267	Not Significant
TLC THS/UL	9.35 ± 5.19	11.12 ± 8.77	-1.253	0.21301	
Neutrophils (In %)	75.95 ± 13.8	76.55 ± 14.56	-0.219	0.82674	
Lymphocytes (In %)	18.83 ± 9.85	19.44 ± 11.44	-0.300	0.76488	
Monocytes (In %)	2.97 ± 1.16	2.83 ± 1.15	0.654	0.51479	
Eosinophils (In %)	1.58 ± 1.59	1.61 ± 1.67	-0.089	0.92891	
Basophils (In %)	0.30 ± 0.17	0.28 ± 0.19	0.417	0.67765	
TRBC millions/cu.mm	4.24 ± 0.73	3.96 ± 0.93	2.142	0.03439	Significant
PCV (In %)	36.78 ± 6.37	33.65 ± 5.97	2.677	0.00857	
MCV (In FL)	85.57 ± 4.69	83.28 ± 7.59	1.851	0.06679	Not Significant
MCH (PG)	26.83 ± 3.61	27.07 ± 3.05	-0.375	0.70830	
MCHC (In gm/dL)	32.46 ± 1.14	32.34 ± 1.16	0.551	0.58253	
RDW-CV (In %)	14.64 ± 2.34	15.25 ± 1.94	-1.517	0.13222	
Platelet Count $\times 10^3/\text{UL}$	202.1 ± 87.5	248.4 ± 116.7	-2.317	0.02235	Significant
PDW (In %)	16.24 ± 0.55	16.29 ± 0.60	-0.220	0.82592	Not Significant
MPV FL	12.51 ± 2.22	12.03 ± 1.88	1.253	0.21274	

Conclusion:

This study showed that a significant number of symptomatic female patients had culture-positive urinary tract infections, with Escherichia coli being the most commonly isolated organism. A high level of resistance was seen against frequently used antibiotics such as Ampicillin,

Ciprofloxacin, and Cefixime, while better sensitivity was observed with Fosfomycin, Nitrofurantoin, and Colistin.

Hematological findings in patients with culture-positive samples showed that many had low hemoglobin, raised TLC, ESR, and other signs of systemic inflammation. Statistically significant differences in ESR, RBC count, PCV, and platelet count between growth and non-growth groups further support the role of these parameters in identifying and monitoring UTIs.

These findings highlight the importance of urine culture and antibiotic sensitivity testing in guiding proper treatment. Hematological parameters can also provide additional support in diagnosis, especially in symptomatic female patients. Regular monitoring of resistance patterns and hematological indicators can help in better clinical decisions and management of UTIs.

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